

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF GREEN BUILDING

Erdanov Panji Nuraliyevich

Lecturer, Termiz State University,
Faculty of Architecture and Construction

Annotation. The article discusses the principles of ecological construction, examining such areas as “green building”, “ecological architecture”, “ecological design”.

Key words: principles, ecology, architecture, construction.

Introduction. Modern construction technologies open up the possibility of building housing, on the one hand, providing people with comfortable living conditions, and on the other, minimizing their negative impact on the environment [1, 2].

The noun “architecture” today has the full right to be accompanied by the adjective “ecological”. And not just because in this case the conversation is specifically about the house and its inhabitants. But also because hidden behind this phrase is an extremely important tendency of man’s desire for nature and nature, which is gaining strength in innovative architecture [5, 8, 9].

The concept of “green building” includes a set of measures aimed at reducing the level of consumption of natural resources during the design, construction, operation of new buildings and reconstruction of dilapidated ones, measures aimed at increasing the comfort of the internal environment of buildings, which is achieved through the efficient use of energy, water and other resources , as well as reducing waste, emissions and other environmental impacts [3, 4, 6].

Ecological architecture is not just a newfangled tradition and a tribute to the times [7, 8]. If we think globally, then ecological architecture is a new way of living and

thinking, the polar opposite of the generally accepted one. For several centuries now, man has been using nature as he pleases.

The tasks of ecological construction include:

- reduction of the total (over the entire life cycle of a building) harmful impact of construction activities on human health and the environment, which is achieved through the use of new technologies and approaches;
- introduction of new technologies, creation of new industrial products;
- reducing the load on regional energy networks and increasing the reliability of their operation;
- creation of new jobs in the intellectual sphere of production;
- reduction of costs for the construction and maintenance of buildings [10, 11, 12].

Green standards are designed to accelerate the transition from traditional design and construction of buildings and structures to sustainable ones, which preaches the following principles:

Environmental safety – reducing the amount of waste and reducing other negative impacts on the environment;

- safety and favorable healthy conditions for human life.

Use of natural natural building materials. The use of exclusively environmentally friendly natural materials and technologies in the construction and operation of the house. It is advisable to use renewable natural materials for construction that are available in the area where the house is being built [13, 14].

Improving the energy efficiency of buildings - measures to reduce heat losses;

- ensuring a hierarchy of rooms that require different temperature conditions and orientation relative to the cardinal points corresponding to each room;
- the need to use renewable energy sources (solar, geothermal energy);
- ensuring optimization of natural ventilation;
- saving existing material resources;
- efficient use of energy, water and other resources;
- favorable location for construction;

- quality of construction;
- principle of integrity.

It is this principle that expresses the ideal of “green” architecture, although, of course, it is not easy to achieve a solution in which all the previously listed approaches to the problem would be involved together.

The emergence of “green” architecture gives a hint that humanity has finally begun to think about the destructive impact on nature, and is gradually trying to learn to coexist with it in harmony.

Ecological design principles can be applied to individual homes, neighborhoods and industrial parks. They can be used to improve existing urban and suburban areas, as well as in the design of new ones. Improving existing areas must begin by addressing issues such as environmental protection, inefficient use of materials, and pollution.

Conclusions. efficiency of materials use, environmental pollution. Humans cannot exist without using natural resources as sources of food, materials, industrial products and energy. The main goal of environmental design is to promote environmental sustainability by adopting ways to produce goods, construct buildings, design large systems such as business and technology parks, reducing the consumption of natural resources and avoiding environmental damage.

References:

1. Akhmedov Zokirjon Jurayevich. (2022). Problems of Increasing the Energy Efficiency of Residential Buildings. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 9, 71–73.
2. Akhmedov, Z. J. (2023). Prospects for the development of ecological housing construction. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(7), 64-69.

3. Akhmedov, Z. J. (2023). Efficient building materials and methods of building construction. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(3), 196-200.
4. Abdumo'minov, O. R., & Akhmedov, Z. (2021). Effect of complex additional and flying ash on cement properties. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 654-658.
5. Erdanov Panji. (2021). Theoretical significance of using national applied arts in the artistic decorsation of interiors. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(8), 171–173.
6. Erdanov, P. N. (2023). Multifaceted structures in architecture. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(7), 70-76.
- Erdanov, P. N. (2023). Sustainable architecture as a vital process. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(3), 201-206.
7. Nuraliyevich, E. P. (2022). Environmental Green Technologies in Architecture and Construction. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 9, 104–107.
8. Panji, E. (2022). Construction and design of smart cities on the example of china. *Results of National Scientific Research*, 1(2), 144–151.
9. Rakhimov Sh.T., Qaziev A. O., Abdumominov O. R., & Akhmedov.Z. J. (2022). Special compounds from industrial waste. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(12), 314–318.
10. Kh, T. F., Bobakulov, A. A., Abdumumunov, O. R., & Ahmedov, Z. J. (2021). Features Of The Structure Formation Of A Filling Mixture Based On Industrial Waste. *The American Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 3(05), 150-155.
11. Shavkat Turdimurotovich, R., Jurayevich, A. Z., & RASHidovich, A. O. (2021). The Development of Compositions and Research of the Properties of Fine Concrete. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 2(9), 138–142.
12. Khusanov, U. S., & Akhmedov, Z. J. (2021). Innovative methods of teaching descriptive geometry in higher education. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 10(10), 649-652.

13. Rakhimov Sh.T., Qaziev A. O., Abdumominov O. R., & Akhmedov.Z. J. (2022). Special compounds from industrial waste. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(12), 314–318.
14. Шарипов Б.Х., Эрданов П.Н. (2021). Сурхон воҳасидаги айрим қадимий меъморий обидалар ҳамда уларнинг меъморий элементлари. *Экономика и социум*, (12), 91.